

AMALIY VA FUNDAMENTAL TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI

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Sefotaksim Antibiotigi Asosiy Komponentining Faol Protein Bilan Molekulyar Dokingi

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada boshqa antibiotiklarga nisbatan chidamli bo'lgan grammusbat va grammanfiy mikroorganizmlarga nisbatan faol bo'lgan, asosiy komponenti sefataksim natriy bo'lgan sefataksim antibiotigini zamonaviy kimyoviy kompyuter dasturlari orqali tahlil qilinib, uning farmakologik xususiyatlari baholangan.

Keywords: Oqsil, ligand, TRPM8, CB-Dock2 online server.

Tadqiqot maqsadi: Sefataksim natriydan ligand sifatida foydalanib biologik faolligini vaqtinchalik retseptor potentsial kation kanalining M suboilasi 8-a'zosi bo'lgan TRPM8 oqsiliga nisbatan o'rganish.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari: Ushbu ishni olib borish uchun kerak bo'lgan modda sefataksim natriy hisoblanadi. Sefataksim natriyning CB-Dock2 onlayn serveri yordamida vaqtinchalik retseptor potentsial kation kanalining M suboilasi 8-a'zosi bo'lgan TRPM8 oqsili bilan o'zaro ta'siri molekulyar doking usulida o'rganildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari:

Vena ichiga va mushak ichiga inyeksiya shaklida eritma tayyorlash uchun kukun shaklidagi sefataksim tarkibida 0.5 grdan -1.0 gramgacha sefataksim natriy mavjudligidan foydalanildi. Antibiotigidan foydalangan holda vaqtinchalik retseptor potentsial kation kanalining M suboilasi 8-a'zosi bo'lgan TRPM8 oqsili bilan CB-Dock2 onlayn serveri yordamida o'zaro ta'sirini o'rgandik [4,5].

CB-Dock2 onlayn serveri yordamida dastlab oqsilning ligand bilan ta'sirlashish bo'shliqlari izlandi, bunda 7198,6940, 4173, 3668 va 2452 Å³ hajmdagi 5 ta faol bo'shliq markazi aniqlandi (1-rasm). So'ng ligand va oqsil serverga yuklanib, molekulyar dokingi amalga oshirildi.

Faol markaz ID	Bo'shliq hajmi (Å ³)	Markaz (x, y, z)	Bo'shliq hajmi (x, y, z)
C1	7198	121, 166, 91	30, 26, 22
C2	6940	87, 122, 91	28, 30, 24
C3	4173	166, 127, 90	27, 24, 23
C4	3668	154, 129, 158	30, 16, 16
C5	2452	127, 127, 67	21, 21, 12

1-rasm. Bo'shliqlarni qidirish natijalari

Oqsil va ligandning o'zaro ta'siridan yuqoridagi keltirilgan bo'shliqlarga mos ravishda -7.5, -6.3; -6.2; -6.0 va -3.7 kcal/mol energiyaga ega faollik kuzatildi (2-rasm). Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki hajmi eng katta va eng kichik bo'shliqda ligandning faolligi yuqori bo'ladi.

Faol markaz ID	Faollik energiyasi	Bo'shliq hajmi (Å ³)	Markaz (x, y, z)	Docking hajmi (x, y, z)
C4	-7.5	3668	154,129,158	35,24,24
C1	-6.3	7198	121,166,91	35,31,24
C2	-6.2	6940	87,122,91	33,35,24
C3	-6.0	4173	166,127,90	32,24,24
C5	-3.7	2452	127,127,67	24,24,24

2-rasm. Bo'shliqlardagi faollik natijalari

C4

C1

C2

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